

ELECTROSTATIC ADHESION FOR ADDED FUNCTIONALITY OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Electrostatic adhesion can be used as a means of reversible attachment. The incorporation of electrostatic adhesion into fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composite structures could provide significant value added functionality. Imparting large potential differences (~ 2 kV) across electrodes generates an attractive force, thus providing a means of attachment. This could be used for latching to external surfaces, or as a means of controllable internal connectivity. Varying the connectivity for discrete elements of the substructure of a given design allows for control of internal load paths and moment of area of the cross section. This could facilitate variable stiffness (both in bending and torsion). Using a combination of existing fabrication techniques functional electrodes have been integrated within a FRP. Copper polyimide thin film laminate material has been both co-cured with Glass fibre reinforced epoxy (GFRP) and bonded to PVC closed cell foam core material to provide a range of structural configurations with integrated electrodes. The ability of such integrated devices to confer variations in global bending stiffness of basic beam structures is investigated. Early testing has shown that the integrated device can generate up to 61% increase in bending stiffness for a simple split-beam configuration.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years there has been a growing interest in multi-functionality of composite structures[1]. Ideally, the material and structure of fibre reinforced composites (FRPs) are produced simultaneously, thus allowing for functional integration at the earliest fabrication steps, fully integrating it into the host structure. Integration of conductive electrode elements allows exploitation of electrostatic adhesion to control the connectivity between discrete substructures. Reversible adhesion in this manner could provide controllable global bending stiffness, a potential high value additional structural functionality.

In this paper, a study is made of the use of electrostatic adhesion for controlled latching of both monolithic and sandwich configuration composite structures. The intention is to assess the achievable change in bending stiffness resulting from the application of electrostatic adhesion at the mid-plane of a variety of beams. Existing research in this field has, to the best of the authors knowledge, only considered the use of electrostatic adhesion in this manner for thin plate structures in bending [2], and only for relatively low forces in sandwich structures [3]. This research aims to consider sandwich structures at higher levels of force to extend the use of such technology to a wider range of applications.

An assessment of the current use of electrostatic adhesion for variable stiffness in FRPs is included. An outline of the fabrication methods used for incorporation of the electrodes into composite sandwich structures is also provided. A demonstration of such devices in three-point bend flexural tests to assess the achievable bending stiffness variation, is provided before considering limitations and further research required.

2 BACKGROUND

Herein is considered the use of electrostatic adhesion for controllable latching of composite

¹ Some or all of contents of this study may be published elsewhere by the authors in the future

structures. Electrostatic adhesion is used here to define the attractive force generated between parallel plates at high potential difference. The configuration of the device is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Basic electroadhesive sandwich device configuration

2.1 Existing Literature

Kuder *et al* provide a relatively comprehensive review of variable stiffness technology for morphing applications [4]. This study considers the use of variable stiffness as a beneficial functionality in its own right, however, the review highlighted the use of Electro-Bonded Laminate (EBL) technology for variable stiffness. Tabatha *et al* [5] presented a variable bending stiffness concept using thin polyimide layers between nickel electrodes. Voltage increases the observed friction between layers, thus increasing bending resistance. This concept was extended by Bergamini *et al* [3-6-7] who focused on replacing permanent adhesion between layers of a composite beam with reversible electrostatic bonding. The experimental methods therein incorporate a dielectric layer, such as polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), between stiffer layers, such as CFRP face sheets. Upon activation of an electric field, a normal holding force is generated, allowing for increased shear stress transfer between the layers as the electric field strength increases, thus increasing bending stiffness.

Whilst the use of electrostatic adhesion to integrate variable stiffness to composite structures is not a novel concept, there is a need for advancements of this technology in terms of achievable stiffness variation and fabrication improvement to facilitate wider applicability. Previously, EBL have been used for vibration suppression [6], with limited investigation into the use of variable stiffness as a function in its own right [2].

The use of EBL for control of internal connectivity has been considered for some adaptive twist concepts. Through controlling the connectivity of spar elements, one can open or close discrete bays of a larger section, thus controlling overall torsional stiffness[8-9]. Thoughtful integration of electrostatic adhesion within a sandwich structure could achieve controllable bending stiffness in a similar manner.

2.2 Structural Concept

Bergamini *et al* summarise the potential means of variable stiffness in a very succinct manner, with three key options: Change in Modulus, Change in Geometry, or Change in Topology[6]. Electrostatic adhesion of discrete elements of the substructure is a means of changing the topology. Considering a basic beam element (Fig. 2(b)), the introduction of a central split with no significant connectivity can drastically reduce the effective second moment of area. For a simple beam section (Fig. 2 (a)) the second moment of area is given below ($b = width$, $d = thickness$).

$$I = \frac{bd^3}{12} \quad (1)$$

For the split beam, the depth of each is half of the complete beam, thus yielding a second moment of area as follows, with each section contributing half of the overall second moment of area (I).

$$I = 2 \frac{b \left(\frac{d}{2}\right)^3}{12} = 2 \frac{b \frac{d^3}{8}}{12} = \frac{2bd^3}{96}$$

$$I = \frac{bd^3}{48} \quad (2)$$

This represents a 75% reduction in bending stiffness if the Young's modulus of each section is equivalent. This effect can be amplified by means of multiple beam splits (Fig. 2(c)), thus the EBL concept [7].

Figure 2: Beam configuration example (a) Solid (b) 2 elements (c) 4 elements

Whilst this variation is significant, this effect can be drastically enhanced via the use of sandwich structures [3]. By locating the split interface within a softer core material, the stiffness modulation between the split and electrostatically bonded configurations is far greater.

2.3 Level of Adhesive Force

In order to effectively switch between the connected and unconnected configurations, the level of shear holding force at the interface is of vital importance. This has been a limitation in existing research using this technology, with the highest level achieved to date in this style of configuration being recorded at just below 0.1 MPa[2]. From earlier work by Di Lillo *et al.*, it is clear that, theoretically, much higher shear forces could be achieved, and thus the connection interface should be designed with the following in mind[10].

Figure 3: (a) Parallel plate configuration (b) Air gap from surface roughness (c) Parallel plate configuration with air gap

For the parallel plate electrode configuration shown in Fig. 3(a) the generated level of normal force from the application of a voltage U can be approximated using the following equation. S is a geometric term for the contact area of the electrodes, and ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space (8.854×10^{-12}). ϵ_r is the relative permittivity of the dielectric layer.

$$P_N = \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r U^2 S}{2d^2} \quad (3)$$

Localised surface roughness and lack of planarity can, however, introduce an air gap between contact surfaces (Fig. 3(b)) [7-11]. This air gap leads to greater separation of the plates than expected, and also introduces a region of lower permittivity (Fig. 3(c)). Thus, from the work of Mao *et al.* a better

approximation for the expected level of holding force (for a given air gap) can be found [12].

$$P_N = \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_{r1} \epsilon_{r2}^2 U^2 S}{2(\epsilon_{r1} d_2 + \epsilon_{r2} d_1)^2} \quad (4)$$

It is assumed that the area (S) and the permittivity of free space (ϵ_0) are constants. In order to maximise the level of holding force, the potential difference (U) should be maximised, the dielectric thickness (d_1) should be minimised, and the relative permittivity of the dielectric (ϵ_{r1}) should be optimised to the air gap thickness. The air gap (d_2) should be reduced to maximise the real contact area, and maximise the holding force. These factors were all considered when designing the composite integrated electrodes. Note that the force generated is a normal force, but the requirement is for shear stress transfer. The coefficient of friction (μ) is thus a multiplier for the above normal force to determine the shear force.

3 DESIGN AND FABRICATION

For this study a co-cure method developed in a previous study to integrate electrode devices into composite structures was used [11]. A thin film laminate of polyimide and copper provides the necessary electrodes for the application of electrostatic adhesion, whilst providing insulation from the host structure.

3.1 Fabrication Method

Samples were produced using a laminate of 35 μm electrodeposited copper on 25 μm polyimide (GTS Flexible Materials Ltd, UK). This material functions as the electrodes either side of the connection interface. For monolithic composite samples, the laminate material was co-cured along with carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) (SE70 carbon epoxy pre-preg, Gurit, UK). For initial composite sandwich samples, 2 mm polyester infusion core (Lantor Soric SF) was co-cured with CFRP pre-preg and, following cure, the electrodes were bonded to the core using an epoxy laminating resin (EasyComposites EL2 Epoxy), and cured at ambient temperature under vacuum for 30 hours. These samples experienced some visible electrode surface waviness and thus alternate core materials were investigated. For the alternative process, the electrode laminate material was bonded to closed cell PVC core foam (EasyComposites EasyCell75) using the same resin and cure cycle. The change of core and curing against an aluminium tool plate provided an improvement in the electrode surface finish. The copper surface was polished post-cure to further improve the surface finish.

Figure 4: (a) Monolithic CFRP with integrated electrodes (b) Sandwich panel using GFRP skins and PVC foam core with integrated electrodes

For each configuration, the electrostatic adhesive interface is located on the centreline of the structure. The core material is used either side of this interface, thus the overall core thickness is that shown in Table 1.

3.2 Design to Maximise Holding Force

The chosen sample geometry is shown in Table 1 with reference to Fig. 1. The geometry was selected to ensure that any variations in bending stiffness introduced by the electrostatic adhesion of the electrode were clearly observable.

The key design choice for maximising the achievable holding force is the choice of dielectric material. A polyester film (Du Pont Mylar A) was chosen as a suitable candidate due to its high dielectric strength (~4kV at 23 μ m), allowing for the use of high voltages at relatively low thicknesses, properties desirable for this application (see Section 2.3). In addition to this, the relative permittivity of 3.2 and friction coefficient of 0.5 were deemed acceptable. An alternative material, a polyethylene terephthalate (PET) film (Mitsubishi Hostaphan RNK) was found, suggesting improved properties compared to the Mylar film. With a dielectric strength of 4.2 kV at 12 μ m and relative permittivity of 3.3, this film was selected for further testing. In order to overcome the electrode surface roughness and maximise the actual contact area between electrodes, a conformal silicone coating (Electrolube DCA) was tested as a potential dielectric. This was applied to one electrode surface by a dip coating method and cured at ambient temperature for 72 hours. In line with existing electroadhesion research, the dielectric was cleaned and softened with acetone prior to testing[13].

Feature		Test F1 Monolithic	Test SA2 Sandwich	Test C1 Core	Test C2 Core	Test CSi Core*
<i>Width (w)</i>	[mm]	30	30	30	30	30
<i>Length (l)</i>	[mm]	150	150	150	150	150
<i>Overlap (L)</i>	[mm]	140	140	140	140	140
<i>Skin Thickness (t_s)</i>	[mm]	0.8	0.8	–	–	0.8
<i>Core Thickness (t_c)</i>	[mm]	0	4	6	6	6
<i>Core Type</i>	–	–	Polyester	PVC Foam	PVC Foam	PVC Foam
<i>Skin Type</i>	–	CFRP	GFRP	–	–	–
<i>Dielectric used</i>	–	Mylar	Mylar	Mylar	Hostaphan RNK	DCA Silicone
<i>Dielectric Thickness (d)</i>	[mm]	23	23	23	12	20XX

*Acetone cleaning prior to testing

Table 1: Test Samples' Geometry and Features

4 EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

4.1 Mechanical Testing

Table 1 shows the five test configurations. A three-point bend flexural test, as shown in Fig. 5, was used to obtain a load-displacement curve for each beam at a variety of applied voltages. A 1 kN load cell connected to an INSTRON 8433 test machine was used to apply the vertical loading at a rate of 10 mm/min up to 5 N. Each Sample was tested with five separate applied voltages: 0, 1, 2, 3 and 4 kV, with ten tests in total for each sample at each voltage. The load-displacement curves from each test can be used to observe the effect of the applied voltage on the global stiffness, and thus the ability of electroadhesive ability to modulate the stiffness.

Figure 5: Three-point bend flexural test configuration

4.2 Electrical Setup

A high voltage DC-DC step up converter (commercially available EMCO *F Series*) was used to impart a high voltage across the integrated electrodes. The basic electrical configuration is shown in Fig. 6. The included potential divider is used as a means to measure the generated high voltage.

Figure 6: Basic electrical setup

5 RESULTS

Three-point bend flexural tests were carried out to assess the operability of the electro-adhesive variable stiffness elements for a range of structural configurations and materials choices. Included results are preliminary and further testing is ongoing.

5.1 Monolithic Sample (Test F1)

Co-curing the copper-polyimide laminate with CFRP produced two thin composite plates with integrated electrode layers, insulated from the host structure. This configuration yielded a change in maximum deflection (at 5 N centre load) of -5.5% with the application of 4 kV across the electrostatic adhesive interface. Whilst this demonstrates a degree of variable stiffness functionality, the effect is limited by this structural configuration. Sandwich structures were thus investigated as likely to achieve a greater performance.

5.2 Sandwich Beam with Polyester Core (Test SA2)

In order to test the effectiveness of integrated electrostatic adhesion in composite sandwich panels, a GFRP skinned polyester core panel was produced, as per Section 3. Fig. 7 shows the increased effect resulting, with a 38% decrease in maximum deflection at 5 N for a 4 kV potential difference imparted. The effect appears to be highly non-linear. The negligible effect at 1 kV may be a result of the step up DC-DC convertor, which is non-linear at the lower end of the 0-12kV operational range. The effective stiffness then increases significantly for the 2 and 3 kV potential difference applications. At 4 kV, the maximum deflection at 5 N only sees a further 7 % decrease compared to the 3 kV application. There are two possible reasons for this. Firstly, this voltage is close to the quoted breakdown voltage of the Mylar dielectric. Small localised breakdowns could limit the actual potential difference across the electrodes, thus limiting the generated holding force. The other reason can be deduced from the shape of the load displacement curve. Initially the higher voltage leads to a greater stiffness of the sandwich

beam, however, at higher loading, the curve flattens and hence a stiffness reduction is observed. This suggests stresses exceeding the holding strength generated are experienced at the interface. The holding strength must, therefore, be lower than expected from theory. Observing the electrode interface surface (Fig. 8), it is clear there is significant variation in the surface quality, and that the interface surfaces are neither flat nor plane. At higher loads, the electroadhesive bond is likely to fail in these locations, and the surface separation resulting from these defects will also reduce the holding force generated.

Figure 7: Load displacement curves for GFRP/Polyester sandwich panel SA2

Figure 8: Surface variations of polyester core mounted electrodes

Whilst the concept of electrostatic adhesion to directly vary bending stiffness of a sandwich panel has been demonstrated, the potential for core improvements to facilitate greater sandwich panel stiffness variation was apparent. The use of a PVC foam core was thus investigated.

5.3 Foam Core Only (Tests C1 and C2)

The chosen PVC foam core had a much more consistent surface compared to the polyester core used in test SA2. When the copper laminate was bonded to this core, a higher quality planar surface was achieved. These PVC foam samples were tested without GFRP skins at this stage for rapid assessment of the operability of the electrostatic interface (Fig. 9).

Figure 9: Load-displacement curves for foam core only three-point bend flexural tests

Note that despite being a monolithic structure as for sample F1, we now obtain a 13% decrease in the maximum deflection at 5 N loading for the 4 kV voltage. This result suggests that should these core structures be integrated in a similar manner to sample SA2, an even greater stiffness modulation might be achieved. Whilst the samples exhibited significant stiffness increases on application of high voltage, the variation observed for 2, 3 and 4 kV was relatively low (~3%). Given the consistency between the gradients of each load displacement curve, the reasoning behind this is unclear at this stage, and requires further investigation.

Figure 10: Load-displacement curves for foam core only three-point bend flexural tests using Hostaphan RNK dielectric film

An alternate thin film dielectric material, Hostaphan RNK, was tested due to its promising quoted properties at a reduced available thickness of 12 μm . Upon the application of a 2 kV potential difference across the electrodes, a 9% reduction in maximum deflection is observed (Fig. 10). This is a very minor increase compared to the deflection reduction using the Mylar dielectric film, which is unexpected given the large reduction in dielectric thickness (see Section 2.3). It is, therefore, possible that the minimum electrode separation distance is being limited by another feature in the configuration, such as improperly trimmed edges, or lack of planarity of the electrode faces.

Another feature of note is that initially the 1 kV and 2 kV load-displacement curves (Fig. 10) appear similar but at around 2 N the 1 kV there is a reduction in gradient, leading to a larger maximum displacement. This highlights that the holding force affects the stiffness profile in two ways. Firstly, a stronger holding force across the interface should lead to a steeper load-displacement curve, denoting a higher overall bending stiffness. The level of holding force generated will also determine the maximum shear stress that can be transmitted via the interface. Above this value, a pseudo-plastic stick-slip failure mode is observed, hence a flattening of the load-displacement curve, an effect referred to as “softening” by Bergamini *et al*[3]. Values could not be obtained for >2kV due to early dielectric breakdown of the Hostaphan RNK. Given the suggested dielectric strength of 4.2 kV, this was unexpected, and investigation into this is yet to be completed.

5.4 Silicone Dielectric (Test CSi)

In order to further increase the holding force generated across the electrostatic interface, inspiration was taken from existing research which used electrostatic adhesion for wall climbing robotics[14-15]. These studies used a silicone dielectric, yielding reasonable levels of shear holding force against a range of substrates. A silicone dielectric benefits from an increased friction coefficient, allowing for greater shear holding force from the generated normal force, and can help to overcome some degree of surface roughness and waviness due to its conformability. Even at a relatively low voltage of 1 kV an 11% reduction in maximum deflection at 5 N (Fig. 11) was observed. Higher voltage values were not obtained due to early dielectric breakdown at the edges of the electrodes. This was due to improper coating and suggests the need for an improved coating method.

Figure 11: Load-displacement curves for foam core only three-point bend flexural tests using conformal Silicone dielectric

6 FUTURE WORK

Further research will consider potential applications for such electrostatically controlled variable stiffness composite structures. Maximising the real contact area through core shape manipulation and dielectric choice is also an area of great interest. Refinement of the fabrication process is also required to ensure maximum fidelity of component geometries, and reduced variation in performance of the variable stiffness devices.

7 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we have demonstrated electrostatically modulated variable stiffness functionality in composite sandwich structures. A reduction in maximum deflection of 38% for a three-point bending configuration was demonstrated for a GFRP skinned polyester core sandwich panel when a 4 kV voltage was applied across integrated electrodes. This is equivalent to an effective 61% stiffness increase. The use of a copper polyimide laminate thin film material allows for the inclusion of low profile electrode elements that are insulated from the host structure. The fabrication method for such incorporated devices is relatively simple when compared to the lamination and cure cycle required for standard FRP composite sandwich panel production. Amendments to the core material, dielectric material and fabrication process showed promising results for variable stiffness potential in monolithic foam tests, with 11% maximum deflection reduction at as low as 1kV voltage application. The integrated electrostatic adhesive elements have demonstrated the ability to vary the stiffness of the host structure at higher loads than existing devices. This research is ongoing, and further development is required to optimise the potential of this technology.

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